

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation:

This article analyses the innovative and quite interesting methods we have in teaching English language. We may have a number of teaching methods in between traditional and modern. Everybody has their own understanding and conclusions on teaching English language. But this paper portrays combining this two types how we can make our teaching very effective. We have been completely bounded with traditional methods of teaching and understanding where the present day learners felt uncomfortable a bit. Learner's mind will never be static it is ever growing and ever changing. Whatever the teaching methodology can be, but teaching must be leaners-centred.

Key words:

Orthodox; integral; inquisitive; agitated; jeopardizing; immerse; atmosphere; intuitively; evaluated; database;

In today's world English is taught in a very orthodox manner. The basic teaching is needed. Teaching the alphabets and the formation of the words is essential and a must. But there is something that is even more important. The children must be able to speak the words and understand their meaning before writing them down. The foundation to teach English can only be taught using the orthodox methods of teaching the alphabets and the words and the rules. But then teaching only the rules is found to be boring by most students and it is because of this that they lose interest in learning the language. Although there is no way other

than the traditional one to teach the basics of the language these methods must be tweaked a bit so as to appeal to the students. When it comes to teaching English to students of higher classes who already know the basics the traditional methods generally tend to yield poorer results than innovative methods. This has already been proven by methods implemented like use of stories, poems, movies, books and newspapers etc. These methods help the students learn the language better without them actually realizing and also it keeps their interest. This article will provide a few of such methods to teach English Language.

Stories form a very integral part of teaching a language. These stories help teach the students about the formation of sentences and how to express their thoughts and a lot of other things and plus they help in keeping the students interest alive as the story's end is something that every student wants to know. It appeals to the inquisitive nature of the students. Any unfinished story always keeps the mind of the reader agitated.

Conversations are by far the most useful ways of teaching the language. When a child learns his or her mother tongue it is by the conversations that takes place between them and others or by listening to the conversations made by the others. The child is never taught the language but is still able to percept the meaning and learns it automatically to use it in day to day life. No one ever teaches the kid the characters of the language or how to make sentences or the grammar of that language. The conversations alone teach the children.

Teaching through games is a very interesting method of teaching. Students and children generally tend to like games and want to play them more and more. Traditional methods dictated for study and games to be separate but the fact remains that the students tend to be more interested in playing games rather than sitting down to study. Any logical reasoning would dictate us to combine the two aspects to solve the problem. The games part of learning would help the students keep their interest as the desire to win is very strong. It keeps us going and when

included with different aspects of learning the learning process would continue almost throughout the day without the children getting tired or bored of studying.

Most of the times competitions like debates and elocutions also help the help the students a lot in learning the language as the aspect of the competitions keep them at the best in conversations. It forces them to use the best possible construction of sentences to put forward their opinions and to use good vocabulary etc. This is a very important tool in helping them learn the language. Also these competitions help them address large crowds which is again is a very important part of personality development. They help us express our emotions. They help us explain what we want. They help us to communicate and hence are the prime tools to express who we are. Thus the knowledge of a language and its proper utilization is very important as it defines us.

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